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PINILISA RICE (*Oryza sativa*) WINE

Haide N. Marinay, Rachele A. Monzon, Marissa G. Lampitoc

Abstract

Pinilisa Rice wine is purple-colored rice that is abundant in Jones, Isabela. With this, the study aimed to develop Pinilisa rice wine. This study was conducted at Brgy. Villa Fermin, Echague, Isabela from the period of November 15 - December 17, 2021. Three treatments were used in making Pinilisa rice wine. There were 30 respondents who were drinking wine who participated in this study for the sensory evaluation. A 9-point Hedonic Scale was used to evaluate the acceptability of the three treatments. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) or F-Test, Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), mean and descriptive statistics were used to test if there was a significant difference between the treatment samples in terms of color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability. The results revealed that in terms of color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability, Treatment 3 got the highest mean score and a final descriptive rating of "like extremely"; therefore, treatment 3 was the most acceptable in all the quality attributes. Also, treatment 3 was the most acceptable treatment, with a final descriptive rating of "like extremely." In all the sensory evaluations conducted, Analysis of Variance showed a highly significant difference among the three treatments. Based on the Return on Investment (ROI), results showed that ROI was relatively different for each treatment. To conclude, each treatment can have a positive venture, as demonstrated by the ROI computed.

Keywords: *Pinilisa Rice, acceptability, treatments, Rice wine*

INTRODUCTION

According to the Municipal Agriculture of Jones, Isabela (2018), Pinilisa rice is a unique, organic plum-colored rice known in other countries, especially in its local town, Jones, Isabela. Pinilisa rice has a unique fragrance and flavor compared to ordinary rice. Unlike other varieties that rely on synthetic commercial fertilizer to grow, Pinilisa is a rare breed that thrives with just rainwater and natural compost. The rice is so unique that the unhulled grain has an awm (ibu) at the tip and its hull is rough and hairy, which serves as protection against the attack of pests and birds at maturity or ripening stage. The panicle is prominent for it has a long peduncle and drooping flag leaf. The grain is classified as "bilog" being round in shape. The once unknown rice variety, now called "Pinilisa", is continuously gaining popularity and acceptance in the province and throughout the region because of its aroma, palatability, and superior quality. This variety is not only cooked pure but is also blended with other commercial varieties at a ratio of 1:2; 1:3; Or 1:4 (one-part pinilisa-two parts commercial rice; one-part pinilisa three-or four-parts commercial rice) depending on one's preference (Domingo, 2018).

With this, the researchers had decided to develop a product from their local, which is

Pinilisa rice wine. Beautifully hued and packed with nutrition, purple rice is ancient heirloom rice with origins in Asia. Its grains are inky black in color when raw. As it cooks, the grains turn a deep iridescent purple. Also known as black rice, forbidden rice, and emperor's rice, legend has it that purple rice was originally reserved exclusively for China's ancient emperors. This may have been because of its appearance or rarity. Purple rice was a difficult crop to grow, and it may have been less available as a food source than other types of rice. Like all rice species, purple rice originates from Japanese rice and is technically a type of grass seed. Its cultivation can be traced back as far as 2500 B.C. The darkly colored grains may have been the result of a mutated rice gene. Purple rice is available in two forms – as long-grained, jasmine rice, and as sticky (glutinous) rice. Both forms are gluten-free (Barrell, A. 2019, November 5).

With this, this study aimed to develop rice wine from Pinilisa. Rice wine is a traditional alcoholic beverage in many parts of Asia. It is produced by microbial fermentation of steamed rice with yeast and water. Furthermore, Rucker (2007) stated that since rice wine is a fermented product, it is not surprising that the drink also contains many strains of lactic acid bacteria (LAB), which are often considered probiotic. Rice wine is an alcoholic beverage fermented and distilled from rice, traditionally consumed in East Asia, Southeast Asia, and South Asia. Rice wine is made by the fermentation of rice starch that has been converted to sugars. Microbes are the source of the enzymes that convert the starches to sugar. Rice wine typically has an alcohol content of 18-25% ABV. Rice wines are used in East Asian, Southeast Asian, and South Asian gastronomy at formal dinners and banquets and in cooking (Dbpedia.org 2022). This developmental study aimed to produce wine from pinilisa rice and to determine the level of acceptability among the respondents and the people who drink it. The literature provides in-depth information about the history, nutrients, and health benefits we can have on Pinilisa rice wine. The possible acceptability of the product for wine or liquor drinkers may encourage them to buy local products and cheap but delicious wine. Its acceptability can also contribute to every occasion. As far as we know, every occasion has a drinking party, and this Pinilisa rice wine will be cost-effective.

The research started with preparing all the materials needed, washing the pinilisa rice, adding the exact amount of water, then cooking. When the pinilisa rice is already cooked, spread the pinilisa rice on a cooking sheet to easily cool down, and combine the yeast and sugar with the pinilisa rice. In a clean container, put the combined ingredients in an airtight container. Store the pinilisa rice in a dark place, and ferment for 14 days. After 14 days, strain the pinilisa rice wine. In a sterilized bottle, pour the strained pinilisa rice wine. Let the pinilisa rice wine ferment for another 14 days, then it is ready to be served. The taste of the pinilisa rice wine changes the longer it ferments. As one lets the wine ferment, it becomes less effervescent and sweeter and smoother.

Statement of the Problem

This study was conducted to determine the acceptability of Pinilisa Rice (*Orayza sativa*) wine.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process of making Pinilisa rice wine?
2. What is the respondent's level of acceptability on the Pinilisa rice wine in terms of

color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture and general acceptability?

3. Which among the three treatments is the most acceptable in the development of the Pinilisa rice wine?
4. What is the computed the Return on Investment (ROI) of Pinilisa Rice wine?

Hypothesis of the Study

There is no significant difference in the three treatments of developing Pinilisa Rice wine in terms of color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability.

Scope and Delimitation

The study was limited to the use of Pinilisa rice in making wine. The products made use of an acceptability test using the 9-Point Hedonic Scale in terms of color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability.

Literature Review

Origin of Pinilisa Rice

Based on the research conducted by Domingo (2018), during the middle part of the 20th Century, there was an Ilocano from Ilocos, Norte who migrated and lived in Barrio Divinan in the town of Jones. This couple possessed the true characteristics and traits of a genuine Ilocano, that of being hardworking, rising early from bed every morning to attend to their farm activities because for them, every minute of the day counted. Since the town was predominantly agricultural, they relied on farming as their source of living. They did kaingin farming in forested areas and planted crops following the drill or "insud-sud" method for they could not plow the area because of the presence of stubbles. Since they were adapted to Ilocos condition, they raised other crops such as vegetables (legumes and cucurbits), root crops, and bananas, including glutinous corn.

Furthermore, in the early 60s, one of their children got married at Villa Campo, Echague, Isabela. The residents here raised rice and other upland crops for their subsistence. The couple often visited their son and family. During their visits, their interest was taken by what they saw in the upland rice specie, especially after tasting it. When they went back to Divinan, they brought with them palay seeds which serve as planting material. Because of the characteristic of this species which is superior compared to other species raised in the area, yearly cultivation was done. Although it was planted only once a year (July-November), its production was enough to supply the food requirements of the family for the whole year. Moreover, when relatives and friends of the couple learned about this unique rice, most of them got seeds as planting materials and started cultivating. As years went by, this species gained popularity not only in other barrios in town but also in nearby municipalities, although farmers were at a loss because they do not know the variety. For those who have tried cultivating the specie, they agreed to give the name "Pinilisa" in lieu of the name previously given (PUGOT), which was not acceptable to them, in honor of Felisa Medrano, the wife of Miguel Nagasao of Barrio Divinan, the couple who brought the rice to Jones and distributed the seeds as planting materials in the early and mid 60s.

The rice is so unique that the unhulled grain has an awm (ibu) at the tip and its hull is

rough and hairy, which serves as protection against the attack of pests and birds at maturity or ripening stage. The panicle is prominent for it has a long peduncle and drooping flag leaf. The grain is classified as "bilog" being round in shape. Dehulling is done through the use of wooden mortar and pestle ("alsong ken Bayo"). The dehulled grain has a red-violet color that they called "PUGOT" which means dark. When the rice is cooked, it emits a peculiar but pleasant aroma that you always crave for it every time you smell it. Hence, the once unknown rice variety, now called "Pinilisa", is continuously gaining popularity and acceptance in the province and throughout the region because of its aroma, palatability, and superior quality. This variety is not only cooked pure but is also blended with other commercial varieties at a ratio of 1:2; 1:3; Or 1:4 (one-part pinilisa-two parts commercial rice; one-part pinilisa-three- or four-parts commercial rice) depending on one's preference.

Recognizing its potential as a lucrative tourist attraction because of its rarity, Mayor Florante A. Raspado was convinced that it would indeed be to the advantage of its town's eco-tourism to promote the pinilisa rice, hence, the birth of the "Pinilisa Festival" in March 2005. Today, the pinilisa festival is included in the directory of the Department of Trade and Industry among the much-celebrated festivities in the Region depicting the culture and tradition of a town.

Facts about Pinilisa Rice

The Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry (2018) reported that pinilisa rice contains chemical compounds called phenolic, flavonoids, and anthocyanin. These are antioxidant compounds with tremendous health benefits and can reduce the risk of developing various chronic diseases. One serving of purple rice (1/4 cup or 50g) contains approximately 160 calories. Each serving of this type of rice contains 5g of protein and 2g of fiber, and 1g of iron. One reason why purple rice is so good for your health is that it contains anthocyanin pigments (Whelan, C. 2019). These are dark pigments that give black and purple rice its unique color and are found in many fruits and berries. According to the Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology, anthocyanin pigments are powerful antioxidants with medicinal benefits and can help rid the body of free radicals. It is entirely non-allergenic and gluten-free. It can be used in desserts, the purple color is from the antioxidant anthocyanin, which is also found in blueberries, and purple rice can be used in any recipe that calls for rice.

Health Benefits of Pinilisa Rice

This rice contains higher levels of healthy antioxidants compared to white rice. Antioxidants have been shown to promote heart health and may help lower the risk of some cancers. They also help protect the body's cells from harmful free radicals. It also lowers the levels of 'bad' cholesterol by increasing the levels of the good high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol in the body. In addition, it prevents the formation of atherosclerotic plaque formation in the arteries that can lead to heart failure (Whelan, C. 2019, March 8).

Sticky purple rice is a whole grain, meaning the outer bran layer is intact. This makes it high in fiber and slightly nutty in flavor. Fiber is important for regular bowel movements and overall bowel health. Fiber may also help with losing weight and lowering cholesterol and blood pressure.

Furthermore, it is an excellent dietary fiber. It helps the digestive system work properly

and prevents constipation and acid reflux. It is also rich in iron which is necessary to make red blood cells, which carry oxygen around the body. A diet lacking in mineral can lead to iron deficiency anemia. Men aged 19 to 64 and post-menopausal women should consume 8.7 milligrams (mg) a day. Younger women, or those who lose a lot of blood during their monthly period, need more iron and should try to consume 14.8 mg a day through their diet.

Moreover, it is also an antioxidant. Purple rice's color is created by a flavonoid called anthocyanin pigment. This same pigment gives blueberries, eggplants, and other healthy fruits and vegetables their deep color. Anthocyanin is a phytochemical found in plants.

They may also have anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic properties. A powerful antioxidant, anthocyanin, has been linked to reducing diabetes, obesity, and heart disease cases.

Lastly, it is a good source of protein. Purple rice is a good source of protein, making it an excellent addition to a vegetarian diet. Protein helps reduce muscle loss by helping the body build and repair muscle tissue. It also helps with cell growth and keeps bones strong.

Difference of Pinilisa/Purple Rice to Other Types of Rice

According to Whelan (2019), there are about 200 calories per 1/3 cup of sticky purple rice. However, the calorie count may vary by brand. Brown rice has about 82 calories per 1/3 cup. Like all other forms of rice, purple rice is gluten-free. Like brown rice, purple rice is a whole grain. Most of the fiber and nutrients are contained in the bran and germ. White rice is a refined grain, meaning the bran and germ are removed. This makes it less nutritious. From a nutritional standpoint, brown and purple rice are both preferable to white rice. However, enriched white rice has some of the nutrients put back in that were removed during processing. All types of rice are rich in carbohydrates. People concerned about diabetes should opt for higher fiber options, which may reduce the impact carbohydrates have on blood sugar. Purple and brown rice have similar amounts of fiber but should only make up a part of the daily fiber requirements. The daily fiber recommendation is between 20 and 25 grams for women and between 30 and 40 grams for men. You should also include other types of fiber in your diet.

Purple rice usually has a higher iron content than brown rice. However, it can vary between brands, so be sure to read nutrition labels. Neither brown nor white rice contains anthocyanin pigments, the substance that gives purple rice its high antioxidant content. Brown rice contains antioxidants, but it may not have the same high levels as purple rice. Both purple and brown rice may contain trace amounts of arsenic, a toxin that is absorbed from the soil. Arsenic amounts are largely determined by where rice is grown. White rice has less arsenic contamination because its outer layer is removed. If you have concerns about arsenic in your rice, rinsing it several times prior to cooking may help to remove it (Arnarson, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The developmental and experimental research design was used in this study. The research entailed the creation of a product and the assessment of its acceptability. This approach measured the level of acceptability of Pinilisa Rice wine among respondents in terms of color/appearance, taste/flavor, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability. Likewise, it

also tested if there is a significant difference in the acceptability of Pinilisa Rice wine.

Research Setting and Samples

This study was conducted at Brgy. Villa Fermin, Echague, Isabela. The acceptability of the product was tested among 30 respondents who are drinking wine with the age bracket of 15-20 years old, 21-25 years old, 26-30 years old, 31-35 years old, 36-40 years old, 41-45 years old, and 51-55 years old.

Statistical Treatment

The data collected were analyzed following the Randomized Complete Block (RCBD) Design.

Results of the sensory evaluation were statistically analyzed using the one-way classification of the analysis of Variance (ANOVA). F test, mean and descriptive statistics were used to determine if there is a significant difference among the treatments in terms of color/appearance, taste/texture, odor/aroma, texture, and general acceptability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Procedure in Making Pinilisa Rice Wine

The procedure for making Pinilisa rice wine has started with preparing all the materials needed. Wash the Pinilisa rice then add an amount of water for cooking. Water varies in its proportion per treatment. When the pinilisa rice is already cooked, spread the Pinilisa rice on the aluminum sheet for cooling. Combine the yeast with the Pinilisa rice, and afterward, in a clean container, put the combined ingredients in an airtight container. Store the Pinilisa rice in a dark place, and ferment for 14 days. After 14 days, strain the pinilisa rice wine, then pour the strained Pinilisa rice wine in a sterilized bottle. Let the pinilisa rice wine ferment for another 14 days, then ready to serve.

After making pinilisa rice wine following the procedures, the researchers have observed that the difference in the proportion of water in cooking the pinilisa rice can influence its fermentation period. The characteristics of cooked pinilisa rice are hard for Treatment 1, slightly soft for Treatment 2, and very soft for Treatment 3. The more amount of water used in cooking the pinilisa, the more it can ferment easily. Therefore, Treatment 3 ferments easily since it has more water compared to the other treatment.

Table 1. Comparison on the Acceptability of the Different Treatments of Pinilisa Rice Wine

Characteristics	Pinilisa Rice wine.						F	Result
	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃			
	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.	Mean	Desc.		
Color/appearance	8.03b	LVM	8.20b	LVM	8.80a	LE	13.53	**
Taste/texture	8.23b	LVM	8.27b	LVM	8.83a	LE	7.66	**
Odor/aroma	8.20b	LVM	8.10b	LVM	8.80a	LE	8.11	**
Texture	8.00b	LVM	8.27b	LVM	8.73a	LE	11.03	**
General acceptability	8.37b	LVM	8.17b	LVM	8.93a	LE	21.99	**

Note: Means with the same letters are not significantly different from each other.

Legend:

- LE -Like Extremely
- LVM -Like Very Much
- ** - Highly Significant

Sensory Evaluation

Appearance/Color

It shows that Treatment 1 has a mean value of 8.03 with a descriptive rating of "like very much". Treatment 2 got a mean value of 8.20 and a descriptive rating of "like very much" while Treatment 3 obtained a mean score of 8.80 with a descriptive rating of "like extremely". Therefore, treatments 1 and 2 got the same descriptive rating while treatment 3 got a high mean score in which respondents like it extremely. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) indicates that there is a highly significant difference in the appearance of the different treatments of Pinilisa rice wine. This means that the difference in the proportion of Pinilisa rice can create a highly significant difference in terms of color/appearance.

Taste/Flavor

It can be seen from the Table that Treatment 3 had the highest mean score of 8.83 with a descriptive rating of "like extremely". This was followed by Treatment 2 with a mean of 8.27 which has the descriptive rating of "like very much" then Treatment 1 had a mean score of 8.23 with a descriptive rating of "like very much". To conclude, Treatment 3 has the most acceptable taste/flavor based on the respondents of this study. Based on the result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), there is a highly significant difference in the taste/flavor of the three treatments of Pinilisa rice wine. Treatment 3 got the highest acceptability in terms of taste/flavor, which is statistically different from both treatments 1 and 2. Results imply that Treatment 3 has the highest acceptability in terms of the taste of Pinilisa rice wine though Treatments 2 and 3 are also acceptable.

Aroma

Based on the table, it can be inferred that the aroma of Treatment 1 with a mean of 8.20 can be classified under "like very much". Treatment 2 is also classified under "like very much" with a mean of 8.10, and Treatment 3 had a descriptive rating of "like extremely" with a mean of 8.80. Therefore, Treatment 3 odor/aroma has been liked extremely among the other treatments.

The Analysis of Variance indicates that there is a highly significant difference in the aroma acceptability of the three treatments of Pinilisa rice wine. As shown in Table 2, Treatment 3 is significantly different from Treatment 1 and Treatment 2. However, Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 do not vary significantly from each other.

Texture

The texture of Treatment 1 is described as "like very much" with a mean of 8.00. Treatment 2 has a mean of 8.27 and is also under the range of "like very much". Treatment 3 differs from the two treatments and falls under "like extremely" with a mean of 8.80. Treatment 1 got the lowest mean score, followed by Treatment 2. Therefore, treatment 3 got the highest mean score which is the most acceptable treatment in terms of texture.

Based on its ANOVA result, there is a highly significant difference in the texture of the three treatments of Pinilisa Rice wine as gleaned from the table. Treatment 3 has the highest acceptability value compared to treatments 1 and 2.

General Acceptability

In general, it can be concluded that Treatment 3, with the highest mean of 8.93, is

highly preferred by the respondents and has a descriptive rating of “like extremely”. This is followed by Treatment 1 with a mean of 8.17, which has a rating of “like very much”. Treatment 2 got a mean score of 8.17, which comparably has the lowest value based on the result. It shows that the general acceptability of Pinilisa rice wine is in Treatment 3. Respondents preferred it more than the other two treatments.

Analysis of Variance shows a highly significant difference among the three treatments regarding the general acceptability. A comparison of means shows that Treatment 3 got the highest mean score compared to Treatments 1 and 2. This highly significant difference in Treatment 3 is because of the adjustments and proportions in terms of ingredients. Therefore, it can say that the more Pinilisa rice is fermented, the more it can produce the most acceptable Pinilisa rice wine.

Most Acceptable Treatment

It shows that Treatment 1 got a mean score of 8.37 with a descriptive rating of “like very much”. Treatment 2 has an 8.17 mean score with a descriptive rating of “like very much”, and Treatment 3 has an 8.93 mean score that describes “like extremely”. Based on the results, it can be concluded that Treatment 3 is the most acceptable treatment in making Pinilisa Rice wine. This treatment has used more proportion of ingredients as compared with the other two treatments, which also differ from each other ingredient’s proportion. Therefore, the more Pinilisa rice, the more it can be acceptable. The Analysis of Variance result shows a highly significant difference among the three treatments regarding the most acceptable treatment. The table clearly shows that Treatment 3 has the highest mean score. Therefore, it is the most acceptable treatment among the other treatments. Respondents prefer its taste, color, odor, aroma, and general acceptability. Treatment 3 gained the highest descriptive rating which is “like extremely”.

Table 2. The Most Acceptable Treatments of Wine as Influenced by Varying Rates of Pinilisa Rice

Treatments	Most Acceptable Treatment	Interpretation
Treatment 1	8.37b	Likely Very Much
Treatment 2	8.17b	Likely Very Much
Treatment 3	8.93a	Like Extremely
ANOVA RESULT	Highly Significant	
C.V. (%)	5.47	
LSD Value	0.32	

Note: Means with the same letters are not significantly different from each other.

Cost and Return Analysis

Table 3 presents the cost and return analysis of the three (3) different treatments for making Pinilisa rice wine. The cost of ingredients that is Pinilisa rice and Rice yeast cake, was based on their prevailing prices during the conduct of the study.

The cost and return analysis of Pinilisa rice wine preparation with three treatments are summarized in Table 4. Each item was computed as to the extent of production per given preparation from the three-treatment sample.

Results show that ROI is relatively different in each treatment. Treatment 1 has 41% ROI, treatment 2 has 33% ROI, and treatment 3 has 27% ROI. To conclude, each treatment can have a positive venture, as shown by the ROI computed.

Table 3. Cost and Return Analysis of the three treatments

	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Number of Packs	1	1	1
A. LABOR			
Cook	80.00	80.00	80.00
LPG	10.00	10.00	10.00
Label	15.00	15.00	15.00
Bottle	20.00	20.00	20.00
Fare	30.00	30.00	30.00
Disposable gloves and Cling wrap	15.00	15.00	15.00
Sub-total	170.00	170.00	170.00
B. INPUT			
Pinilisa Rice (2,500g) @Php.90/kg	75.00	75.00	75.00
Rice Yeast Cake (54g) @Php.100/pack	18.33	33.33	48.33
Sub-total	93.33	108.33	123.33
C. CONTINGENCY (5% of A+B)			
COST OF PRODUCTION	276.50	292.25	308.00
GROSS INCOME	390.00	390.00	390.00
NET INCOME	113.50	97.75	82.00
ROI (%)	41	33	27

* 1 bottle per treatment (750 mL)

* P390.00 SRP

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were derived:

1. In terms of color /appearance, Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 had a final descriptive rating of "like very much". At the same time, Treatment 3 got a final descriptive rating of "like extremely"; therefore, Treatment 3 was the most acceptable in terms of color /appearance. The result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) indicated that there was a highly significant difference in the appearance of the different treatments of Pinilisa rice wine.
2. In terms of taste/flavor, Treatment 3 had the highest mean with a descriptive rating of "like extremely"; thus, respondents liked it the most. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result indicated that there was a highly significant difference in the taste/flavor of the three treatments of Pinilisa rice wine.
3. In terms of odor/aroma, Treatment 3 got the highest mean score and a descriptive rating of "like extremely". The Analysis of Variance result indicated a highly significant difference in the odor/aroma acceptability of the three treatments of Pinilisa rice wine.
4. In terms of texture, Treatment 3 got a final descriptive rating of "like extremely". To conclude, it was the most acceptable in terms of texture. Based on its ANOVA result, there was a highly significant difference in the texture of the three treatments of Pinilisa Rice wine.
5. In terms of general acceptability, Treatment 3 got the highest mean score and a final

descriptive rating of "like extremely". Treatment 1 had a mean score higher than treatment 2, but both had descriptive ratings of "like very much". The result of the Analysis of Variance showed a highly significant difference among the three treatments regarding their general acceptability.

6. Based on the result, Treatment 2 was the least preferred in making Pinilisa rice wine, followed by Treatment 1 though they got a final description of "like very much". Treatment 3 got the highest mean score and a final descriptive rating of "like extremely". Therefore, Treatment 3 was the most acceptable treatment in making Pinilisa rice wine.

7. Results showed that ROI was relatively different in each treatment. Treatment 1 had 41% ROI, Treatment 2 had 33% ROI, and Treatment 3 had 27% ROI.

Recommendations

Based on the results obtained from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. This research recommends further studies to include testing on the alcohol content of Pinilisa Rice wine.
2. This study also suggests conducting a microbial test on the wine to identify contaminants and microbes.
3. A study on the shelf-life of Pinilisa rice wine is also recommended and must be conducted to determine if the taste will be different.

Reference Cited

- Arnarson A. (2017, June 4). Arsenic in Rice: Should you be concerned? Healthline. <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/arsenic-in-rice>
- Barrell, A. (2019, November 5). Purple Rice: Health benefits, calories, and nutrition. Medical News Today. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/319958>
- Domingo, A. B. (2018). The PINILISA festival. Mun. of Jones. <https://www.jones-isabela.com/the-pinilisa-festival>
- Rice wine. (n.d.). Dbpedia.org. Retrieved January 16, 2022, from https://dbpedia.org/page/Rice_wine
- Rucker, M. (2007, October 11). Rice wine health benefits and its effects on the body Mike Rucker, ph.D... Mike Rucker, Ph.D. <https://michaelrucker.com/functional-supplements/rice-wine-health-benefits/>
- Whelan, C. (2019, March 8). Purple Rice: Health benefits, nutrition, and calories. Healthline. <https://www.healthline.com/health/purple-rice>
- Purple Rice Many Health Benefits, Reduces Obesity (2019) <https://mimahealth.com/purple-rice-health-benefits-reduces-obesity>
- Is Purple Rice Good for You? 10 Health Benefits, Side Effects (2021) https://www.medicinenet.com/is_purple_rice_good_for_you/article.htm

